

ISSN 0975-4067

KIRANĀVALĪ

Journal of Sanskrit Research Foundation

The New Triyandrum Sanskrit Series
Vol. XIV, Book. III -IV

JULY - DECEMBER 2022

SRF

किरणावली
Sanskrit Research Foundation
Thiruvananthapuram

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Śākta Brahmins of Kerala and their rituals with esoteric and exoteric dimensions

Dr. Ajithan. P. I¹

It is a well-known fact that Kerala inherited a distinct temple ritual cult. Broadly this can be divided into three traditions i.e., *Tantrasamuccya*, Irinjalakkuda and Śāktism of *Piṭāras* (bhaṭṭāraka) and *Mūssads*. The former, *Tantrasamuccaya* tradition, consists of all the similar ritualistic traditions that took their root either before or after the composition of the *Tantrasamuccaya*.² This tradition gained wider acceptance and dominance all over Kerala.³ With regard to Irinjalakkuda tradition it is a less known cult, geographically constrained and prevalent only among the brahmin settlements of this specific region. Though in practice Irinjalakkuda settlement follows a different custom of temple rituals, there are similarities with that of *Tantrasamuccaya*.⁴ While *Tantrasamuccaya* and

1. The scholar Ajithan.P.I is the awardee of the ICSSR Post-Doctoral Fellowship. This paper is largely an outcome of the Post-Doctoral Fellowship sponsored by the Indian Council of Social Science Research (ICSSR). However, the responsibility of the facts stated, opinions expressed, and the conclusion is entirely of the author.
2. Though *Tantrasamuccaya* is a ritual manual, later it turned out to be representative of a specific temple ritualistic tradition of Kerala. The temple ritual cult of Taraṇanallur, Puṭayūr, Kuzikkāṭṭu etc. can be included into this group.
3. The naimittika (incidental) rituals like jīrṇoddhāra and utsava performed in most of the temples of Kerala are based on *Tantrasamuccya*.
4. The sole printed source to refer to ritual peculiarities of this tradition is *Saṅgamagrāmapaddhati* (published by Irinjalakkuda Kamakoti Yajurveda Pāṭhaśāla, 2020), which is in fact, based on note prepared by Pantal Damodaran Vaidikan, a vedic priest by profession. Taraṇanallūr Padmanābhan Nampūtiri, tantrin of Trprayar Sriramswamy Temple, holds the view that Nārāyṇātmakam (available at www.shripuram.org in PDF format) is the source text of

Irinjalakkuda traditions have many things in common, the Śākta tradition of *Piṭaras* and *Mūssads* is totally distinct from both.

Śākta Brahmins

If the carriers of *Tantrasamuccaya* and Irinjalakkuda traditions are orthodox brahmins of Kerala, that of Śākta tradition are *Piṭaras* and *Mūssads* who are known as Śākteya brahmins. It is due to the fact that they are the worshippers of Śakti, follow the vedic rites of passage (*samskāras*), perform daily and incidental rituals as exactly orthodox brahmins of Kerala do,⁵ they are called as Śākta brahmins. Though brahmins by birth they are not considered to be equal to orthodox brahmins of Kerala and have been degraded to a secondary status. It is believed that these brahmins form a migratory group, descendants of Kashmir brahmins⁶ whose trajectory of exodus and time of their settlement could not be traced yet. But eventually they preferred Kerala as a final abode to settle. Not only do they form a different group, they also possess a different ritual cult as well. Unfortunately, no study has been so far undertaken on these facts.⁷

Irinjalakkuda tradition.

- 5 The smārta rituals of passage of *Piṭaras* is similar to Bauddhāyana ritual cult of Kerala brahmins. The difference is minimal and which makes them apart. In a private conversation, Keśavan Mūssad has revealed that any smārta ceremony in their family is preceded by the performance of a Śākteya pūjā.
- 6 This is postulated on the basis of the tantric ritual cult they inherit. Another instance which shows the connection between these temples and Kashmir is that the commencement festival ritual of *Matayikkavu* had been marked by the arrival of *Virālipattū* from Kashmir. According to C.M.S Chenthera, *Piṭaras* are those who have been brought to Kerala from Bengal by the King Kolathiri for conducting Śāteya pūjā in his territory, Kolathunadu, northern Malabar. Uttarakeraḷattile Śākteyakkāvukal, p. 14. It is believed by some of *Piṭaras* that they migrated from Tiruchirappalli, Tamilnadu.
- 7 The focus of previous studies that have been undertaken by eastern and western scholars was on the exoteric realm of Śākta temples of Kerala. Though Maciej Karasinski-Skora has tried to expose the influence of the Tripurā cult on the ritualistic practices of these temples, he has not explored the Krama influence in detail. See his thesis (unpublished) *Śākta Tantric Traditions of Kerala- its Peculiarities and Development Under the Impact of Śrividya* for more details. The other studies related to Śākta temples of Kerala are: Renjini. M.V., *Worship of Female Deities in Kerala Tantric Texts: A Socio-cultural Study* (submitted to Department of Sanskrit, Calicut University) and Muralikrishnan M.V., *Critical Edition and Study of Mātṛsadbhāva* (submitted to Department of Vedanta, Sree Sankaracharya University of Sanskrit, Kalady)

It is interesting to note that though a small community, *Piṭāras* and *Mūssads*, reside around the Śākta temple, as four independent families. For instance, the four households around 'Kalarivatukkal' temple are *Tāzattillam*, *Kizakkillam*, *Pazeḍattillam* and *Vadakkillam* named accordingly based on directions and relative positions of the houses with regard to the temple.

A similar pattern is observed across all other major Śākta temples too.⁸ They formed an independent caste-like structure with their own chief vedic priest called *vādhyān* who supervises all the smārta ceremonies like upanayana, vivāha etc., and teaches temple rituals to the next generation. He also acts as an authority to declare that someone is eligible to perform Śākta rituals in temples. The Śāktas have their own special cremation grounds shared only within these families. After the cremation the remaining skeletons are buried at a location in the vicinity of the temple called *Tirunelli*, which is common for all the Śākta families, is the place where all the posthumous observations are made every year. With regard to their priesthood, there is a family of *tantrins* called *tantrimūssad* who maintain a hierarchy among themselves. Someone who performs all the major rituals in temples are known as *mūttapiṭāra* and the one who assists the former is known as *īlayapiṭāra* (*laghubhaṭṭāraka*) and *piṭāra*. All these different priestly groups play different roles, depending on the nature of rituals.

The marital alliance is made only within their clan who lie spread in and around Talipparamba, Payyannur, Kannur and Kozhikkode districts of Kerala. They are Yajurvedins belonging to the Bauddhāyana clan.⁹ Though they follow Kerala Brahmins closely in their vedic observances, minor variations are observed with *upanayana* and *vivāha* ceremonies.

8 The four families that settled around Matayikkavuvu are Thazhattillam, Naduvile illam, Ayirampalli Illam and Ittammal Illam. Chenthera has pointed out that there are eight families of Piṭāras in Thalipparamba and ten of them in Malabar. The families that have been enlisted by him are: Vaṭakke illam, Tāzattillam, Kizakke illam, Payārattillam, Iṭṭummalillam, Ottappurayil, Āryamballi, Kaliyāmballi, Rāmankulangara and Naḍuvileppāṭṭu. Ibid. p. 16

9 Some of them believe that they belong to Vasiṣṭha gotra whereas, others trace their lineage to Viśvāmitragotra.

Apart from *Piṭāras* and *Mūssads* who form part of Śākta brahmin group, the community of *Aṭikal* is also counted along with them as associated Śākta brahmins. But the details on the extent to which they are close or different from the other two groups, is yet to be explored.

This paper is an attempt to study the tantric ritual cult of Śākta brahmins, particularly its esoteric and exoteric dimensions. The following observations are made on the basis of previous studies, testimony of manuscripts which are located at public and private repositories all over Kerala and interviews with scholars, Śākta priests and historians.

Śākta temples

There are sixteen temples in Kerala where Śākta ritual cult of *Piṭāras/Mūssads* are or were prevalent. They are:

1. Mannampurathukavu, Nileswaram
2. Kalarivathukkal Bhagavati Kshetram, Valapattanam
3. Panamkāvu
4. Madayi Thiruvarkkattukavu (Madayikkavu),
5. Mamanikkunnu Bhagavati Kshetram, Irikkoor,
6. Thalipparamba
7. Sri Vazhuncherrykkavu (Thiruvanchery) Bhagavati
8. Kshetram, Kuthuparamaba.
9. Ammangottam, Srikanthapuram, Irikkoor
10. Pisharikkavu, Kollam
11. Thiruvalayannattukavu, Govindapuram, Kozhikkode
12. Kaliyamvalli, Kozhikkode
13. Kodikkunnu Bhagavati Kshetram, Pallippuram, Pattambi.
14. Thirumandhankunnu Bhagavati Kshetram, Angadippuram,
15. Malappuram
16. Kodungalloor Bhagavati Kshetram, Thrissur
17. Parumala Valiya Panayannarkkavu, Pathanamthitta
18. Muthoottukavu, Thiruvalla
19. Thiruvalayannattukavu, Kottakkal

These temples are known as *Kāvus* (groves) and they maintain a unique architectural structure when compared to other temples of

Kerala.¹⁰ Most of them are situated on the hill tops or surrounded by small forests. It was not easy to reach these temples until the time of temple entry proclamation, which enabled all Hindus to enter into temple premises. It doesn't mean that these temples were totally restricted to laymen, people belonging to all castes were permitted and entitled to exercise their duty during festival season.¹¹ The same is followed even today.

The above 16 temples are connected with each other by the common priesthood and popular local narratives. For example, the temples like Panamkavu and Ammankottam are just annexes of Kalarivatukkal and Mamanikkunnu temples. The goddesses of Kalarivatukkal and Matayikkavu are believed to be sisters. So in many ways Matayikkavu and Kodungallur Bhagavati temples are connected with each other. Among these temples Thirumanthankunnu, Muttuttukavu, Panayannarkāvu and Kodungalloor are taken over by Kerala brahmins but it is learned that Śākta rituals of *Piṭāras* were in practice even in these four temples long before.¹²

Out of these, eight temples of central and north Malabar form a cluster by sharing a common ritual system and similar religious observances. The rest are considered to be belonging to another group because of the fact that they are geographically outside the

10 Generally, Śiva faces east and the goddesses Caṇḍā kāpālīnī, Kālasaṅkarṣiṇī and Bhadrakālī, in the same sanctum sanctorum, are found enshrined on the right side of Śiva (viz., south) facing either north or west directions. Kṣetrapāla is situated on the north-east corner. The goddess Bhadrakālī is worshipped either alone or with the set of Sapta/Aṣṭa mātṛs including Viraabhadra and Gaṇapati. The layout of these temples are totally different from that of other temples of Kerala. The exact difference remains yet to be studied.

11 Fawcett F. in his exemplary work entitled *Nayars of Malabar* delineates the privileges of peoples belonging to each caste who lived around the temple Pesarikkavu in Kollam and how they exercised them during the festival season, as he had been a witness. p. 255 ff. Just like Pesarikkavu, all other Śākta temples maintain this custom even today. So, these temples are a confluence of people of divergent castes that not only consists of upper castes but even marginalised ones.

12 In a private conversation Kesavan Piṭārar communicated that he has heard of someone from his community who had filed a suit in the court claiming that it was their right to perform rituals in Kodungalloor temple, where Aṭikal enjoy the right to worship. But he could not furnish exact details.

cluster and belonging to different priestly community called *Aṭikal*¹³, particularly at Thirumanthankunnu, Kodungalloor and Kodikkunnu temples. Some historians identify *Aṭikal* as descents of ḷankovaṭikal of *Cilappatikāra*.¹⁴ The priests of Valayanattukavu, Pisharikkavu and Kaliyamvalli are known as *Mūssads*. Of these communities, the ritual system of *Piṭāras* and *Mūssads* are same whereas, that of *Aṭikal* is yet to be studied. It is to be noted that forthcoming discussions are mainly restricted to the eight Śākta temples of Malabar, where *Piṭāras* and *Mūssads* enjoy priesthood.

Royal Patronage

Most striking feature of these temples is they enjoyed patronage of local chieftains and stood out as an empowering centre for the kings, be it to subjugate other local kings and expand the kingdom or to be victorious in all royal endeavours. It is said that the Chirakkal King used to visit Panamkavu temple and get his sword ritually empowered before he set out for a battle. Such instances of royal connections to these temples are numerous.¹⁵ Also, chieftains had the rights to nominate and select the chief priests of these temples called *mūtta piṭārar* and his assistants. So royal engagement with these temples and priestly class helped them to sustain even during the hard times of Tippusultan's attack on temples of Malabar. When any member of the local chieftain visits these temples, there are certain customs to be followed by them and that is in practice even today.¹⁶

Pantheon and Ritual

The system of ritual followed in these temples is multi-layered and complex. We have to separate and clearly define each layer at

13 See Edgar Thurston and K. Rangachari, *Castes and Tribes of Southern India* for finding legendary accounts of the origin of Aṭkal community and their customs.

14 See Induchudan, *The Secret Chamber*.

15 See Uttarakeralattile Śakteyakkāvukal; Chelanattu Achyutha Menon, *Keralattile Kāliseva*; and Dr. R. C Karippath, *Teyyaprapaṅcam*.

16 When any male member of Royal family visits the temple he has to keep a small dragger under his shoulder before entering into the inner temple premise. While he visits, no one else is allowed to remain in the temple except the King's assistant and chief priests. He has to keep the sword in this manner until he comes out of the temple premise. When a female member of royal family visits the temple she is not supposed to wear modern dresses but mulakkacha and mundu alone.

the very outset in order to understand the degree of complexity and also the underlying principle by which divergent cults are brought together. The pantheon is almost the same in all these temples though there is slight difference with regard to the presiding deity and number of *upadevatas*. The pantheon consists of Caṇḍā kāpālīnī, Kālasaṅkarṣiṇī, Parā, Bhadrakālī, Sapta/Aṣṭa mātṛs, Śiva, Yogini, Yogeśvarī, Bhairava, Bhairavī, Vetāla and Kṣetrapāla. Except Parā all other deities have a particular substratum of worship which ranges from the iconic form of Caṇḍākāpālīnī, Kālasaṅkarṣiṇī and Bhadrakālī to weapons like trident, khadga (nāndaka) and mirror (mukura).

On the textual sources of these deities, the worship of Caṇḍākāpālīnī can be traced to the *Brahmayāmala* (Picumata) but the fact is that the chief priests of these temples do not practise and possess a complete ritual system of the goddess as laid down in the text. The worship is shortened to bare minimum. The cult of Kālasaṅkarṣiṇī, the goddess of Krama system, is taught in a great number of texts like *Brahmayāmala*, *Kramasadbhāva*, *Kālīkulapañcaśataka*, *Devidvyardhaśatikā*, three *Mahānayaṅprakāśas* (of Śitikaṅṭha, Arṇasimha and an unknown author), *Mahārthamañjarī* of Maheśvarānanda, *Cidgaganacandrikā* of Śrīvattsa, *Kālīkulakramārcana* of Vimalaprabodha and *Mahārthamantrapaddhati*.¹⁷ But the system of *Piṭāras* follows *Mahārthamañjarī* exactly in the order, but in the internal ritual (kulaprakriyā)¹⁸. Therefore it can be safely concluded that the Krama system of Kashmir reached Kerala in well-developed form and it can be traced as such back to *Mahārthamañjarī*, a 13th century A.D South Indian treatise.

Though the worship of Goddess Parā is taught in a varying number

17 See Sanderson, Evidence of the Early Śākta Traditions in the Regions Other Than Kashmir, Handout for a Lecture recorded online on 7 November, 2020 for release on 11 November for the Oxford Centre for Hindu Studies, pp. 9-12.

18 Kulaprakriyā is an internal ritual performed on the body of a practitioner. The external ritual in Kashmir Śaiva lore is known as Tāntrikaprakriyā. The *Mahārthamañjarī* expounds Kulaprakriyā in abridged form but its emphasis is more on explaining the philosophy of the ritual. The manuscripts of Kulaprakriyā that are in the private repositories of Piṭāras exactly follow the order laid down in *Mahārthamañjarī*.

of texts like *Siddhayogeśvarīmata*, *Tantrasadbhāva*, *Trikasāra* and some South Indian scriptures like *Paraśurāmakalpasūtra*, *Nityotsava* and *Anuttarasamvidarcanā carcā*¹⁹, the system of *Piṭāras* is different and short for the focus is mainly on worship of the mantra in one's own body, not in external maṇḍala.²⁰ No textual source for this system is found so far. It is to be noted that the manuscripts found from the private collection of *Piṭāras* lay down elaborate ritual procedure of the goddess Parā but it doesn't feature in the daily rituals of these temples. The reason why the worship is curtailed to the essentials and lost its priority, is not known. Though Śrīcakra is also featured among the above list.²¹ No worship of Tripurasundarī is known to be performed in any of these temples except some flower offerings. But there are manuscripts of a full-fledged Śrīcakrapūjā in some of the households of these priests, which are modelled on the Śaubhāgyamañjarī of Nārāyaṇanātha²², a South Indian Ritual manual of Tripurasundarī. The cult of these four goddesses form part of esoteric tantric practices. Generally, initiation is the sole prerequisite to get entry into these secret traditions according to the scriptures. But interestingly, there is no practice of elaborate standard rituals of initiation among *Piṭāras* nowadays. But it is to be noted that there is specific form of ritual practice called as *kazakam ariyikkal*, which is a reminiscent of Kaula/Krama mode of initiation²³, by which someone from the family of

19 See Sanderson, *ibid.*, p. 7

20 The ritual system of Parā of Piṭāras is totally different from that of any of the available texts. Its origin remains to be traced.

21 Among the substrata of worship, Śrīcakra is also found in some of these temples like Panayannarkavu, Muttuttukavu, Kodungalloor, Vaḷayanatu, Kaliyamvalli and Panamkavu but a full-fledged Śrīcakrapūjā is performed nowhere nowadays.

22 In ten chapters, known as unmeṣas, Nārāyaṇanātha expounds the daily worship of Tripurasundarī, interspersed with elements of Śākta philosophy. At end of the work he provides some autobiographical details as he was a disciple of Viṣṇuvāsudevanātha, who got initiated into Tripurā cult by Śrī Devarājagiri. Śrīmat paramahaṃsaparivrājakācārya kavīṭhācārya cakravartī śrīdevarājagiripūjyapādapraśiṣyasya śrīviṣṇuvāsudevanāthaśiṣyasya śrīnārāyaṇanāthasya kṛtau śrī saubhāgyamañjaryāṃ daśamaḥ unmeṣaḥ.

He also refers to one of his other works as Citravaibhava, which according to the information provided by the author himself is concerned with the theoretical explanation of each syllable of Śrīvidyāmantra.

akṣarārthopadeśastu madukte citravaibhave/

draṣṭavyo atyantaguptosau samvidāgamapāragaiḥ // T. 971. p. 79

23 Alexis Sanderson, A Commentary on the Opening Verses of the Tantrasāra of

Piṭāras after *upanayana* and *samāvartana* rites of passage is made eligible to perform the rites of these temples.

The most remarkable feature of the worship of these esoteric deities is that they form the secret inner realm of *Piṭāras*. They do not reveal this to an outsider unless he/she is more familiar with Trika, Krama, Kaula and Tripurā systems or initiated into any of these esoteric tantric traditions.

The ritual system of Bhadrakālī is the most intriguing one, for, it constitutes the outer civic space. Generally, these temples are known as śakteyya *kāvus* or *kālī* temples. For the general public these are the temples of Bhadrakālī. And further, local customs, art forms like *Theyyam* and other cultural art performances associated with these temples are held around the purānic accounts of valorous deeds of Bhadrakālī.²⁴ And usually the general public is totally unaware of the inner secret worship and its association with the Krama system of Kashmir. The worship of Bhadrakālī is also something very unique. She is worshipped as Rurujit, the killer of demon Ruru, whose cult is slightly different from other systems of Bhadrakālī worship of Kerala. It is easily discernible even in the temple layout and architectural structure. With regard to textual references to peculiarity of such temples, Alexis Sanderson's view that these temples are based on māṭṛtantra cult of *Brahmayāmala*, is worth considering. He notes:

In the early mediaeval period it is, to my knowledge, only in the Māṭṛtantra tradition of the unpublished and hitherto unstudied *Brahmayāmala* texts of southern India that Bhadrakālī comes to the fore as the principal focus of a properly Tantric Śākta cult. And while that cult, in which she is worshipped either on her own or, as Cāmuṇḍā, as one of seven Mothers, accompanied by Vīrabhadra, and Gaṇeśa, is indeed fully Tantric, it is much more integrated into the civic dimension of religion than are the early North Indian Śākta traditions exemplified by the Trika and Kālikula. For unlike these and the northern *Brahmayāmala*, with which it has only a tenuous connection, the subject of these texts is not worship conducted by individual initiates for their own benefit or that of individual clients but a calendrically fixed programme of regular worship conducted

Abhinavagupta, footnote no. 63, pp. 113-14. [...] Similarly in the passage 10, in the Krama-related 4th Ṣaṭka of the Jayadrathayāmala .. ' O fair-waisted one, [the guru] should initiate brāhmaṇas by giving them alcoholic liquor to drink.[...].

24 See Chelanattu Achyutha Menon, Keralattile Kāliseva, pp. 13-21; 113-172.

by professional priests before permanent idols in temples; and the principal purpose of the worship is said to be to foster the victory of the monarch over his enemies, as in the Orissan cult of Bhadrakālī, and, more generally, to protect the kingdom from danger (deśāsāntiḥ, rāṣṭrasāntiḥ), such temples being, at least in the main, royal foundations and recipients of royal patronage.²⁵

The first instance of such a temple based on mātṛtantra can be traced back to Kolaramma temple, Kolar in Nolambavādi if at all it predates Śākta temples of Kerala. A 11th century A.D. inscriptions found in this temple provide a vivid picture of the deities who receive worship every day there.²⁶ They are the Vīrabhadra, Saptamātr̥s, Gaṇapati, Cāmuṇḍeśvarī, Kṣetrapāla, Mahāśāsta, Suryadeva, Yogini and Yogeśvara. It is to be noted that except Sūryadeva, all other deities of Kolārammā temple are found in some of the śākta temples of Kerala too. For example, Śāstā is one of auxiliary deities in Matayikkavu and Yogini and Yogeśvara form part of daily rituals of all of these temples. So the Kolārammā temple might be a prototype of Śākta temples of Kerala. But the difference is that Cāmuṇḍā forms just a retinue of Bhadrakālī along with saptamātr̥s in śākta temples of Kerala, whereas in Kolārammā temple she (ugracāmuṇḍā) is the presiding deity and supreme among saptamātr̥s.

As has been pointed out earlier, the description and classification of temple structures of Rurujit temples first appears in South Indian *Brahmayāmala*. Then the *Mātr̥sadbhāva*, which is modelled and draws heavily on *Brahmayāmala*, elaborate it into *Sāṅga*, *Niraṅga* and *Bhinna* divisions.²⁷ This classification is mainly based on the

25 Atharvavedins in Tantric Territory: The Āngirasakalpa Texts of the Oriya Paippalādins and their Connection with the Trika and the Kālikula, with critical editions of the Parājapavidhi, the Parāmantravidhi and the Bhadrakālīmantravidhiprakāra, pp.277-78.

26 http://idb.ub.uni-tuebingen.de/diglit/EC_10_1905_HD/0492, 108 dated 1071 A.D., [...] "(here follow details of the revenue in gold from the different villages and of its equivalent in paddy.) To each of the deities – Vīrabhadra, Brahmāṇi, Īśvari, Kaumāri, Vaiṣṇavi, Vārāhi, Indrāṇi, Śrī- Cāmuṇḍeśvari, Gaṇapati, Cāmuṇḍeśvari of Mūlasthāna, Yogeśvari, Kshetrapāla-deva, Mahā-śāsta, and Sūrya-deva-4 nālī of rice.[...]"p. 36. I am indebted to S.A.S Sarma for sharing with me the copy of translation of the inscriptions.

27 sāṅge vātha niraṅge vā bhinnevāsyānurūpath// 3
uttarābhīmukhaṃ sāṅgaṃ niraṅgaṃ prāṇmukhaṃ bhavet/
paścimābhīmukhaṃ bhinnamiti tredhānigadyate// 4

direction the goddess faces. *Sāṅga* is that in which the goddess Bhadrakālī faces north, whereas in *niraṅga* she faces east. And if she faces west, it is called '*bhinna*'. One of the distinct features of Rurujit temples is that the goddess is found facing north together with *Sapta/Aṣṭamātr̥s*. Following the lead of *Mātr̥sadbhāva*, Śeṣasamuccaya of Cennas Śaṅkaran Nambūtiri (15th century A.D) explicates it further and lays down specific ritual procedures associated with each of these classifications.²⁸ Even a cursory look at the structure of these temples would reveal that it confirms to the textual references of *Mātr̥sadbhāva* and Śeṣasamuccaya. It is to be noted that apart from these two texts, none of the ancient or mediaeval scriptures of Krama system provides architectural details of such temples. The reason is that the Krama system has nothing to do with temples.

Esoteric Dimension

As has been mentioned above, inner secret ritual space of *Piṭāras* consists of the pantheon of Caṇḍā kāpālīnī, Kālasaṅkarṣiṇī and Parā. Among them Caṇḍā kāpālīnī takes the centre space in these temples.²⁹ Though the *Picumatabrahmyāmala* is the root text of worship of Caṇḍā kāpālīnī, it is not followed as such in daily worship. Among her retinues prescribed in *Brahmayāmala* i.e., four devīs, four dūtis, six yoginis and eight mothers³⁰, only the first set of four yoginis

28 atha svatantrasya yadagrataḥ syād
sāṅgāṃ nijāṅgairnikhilairupetaṃ/
pradhānaprṣṭhocitamāṇḍapaṃ tad
bhinnam vidurnaivamidaṃ svatantram // 7. 1 //
syād prāgāsyāḥ svatantraḥ smarajidiha puro dakṣiṇe paścimāsyā
cāmuṇḍā syācca bhinnā namuciripudigāsyā niraṅgaiva vātha/
devasyāsyāstu vā yāmyadiśi śāśadigāsyā jananyopi sāṅgā-
statprāk sā vaha sāṅgānaladiśi nikhilā mātaro vaha bhinnāḥ// 7. 2 //

It is not known yet how the author of Śeṣasamuccaya extended the structure of Kālī temples into complex ones merely on the account of a reference in *Mātr̥sadbhāva*, where it is silent about such elaborations.

29 The Caṇḍā kāpālīnī takes the center stage in Kalarivatukkal and Madayikkavu temples. But ritual system of *Piṭāras* lays importance to the worship of Kālasaṅkarṣiṇī in general.

30 See Shaman Hatley, *The Brahmayāmalatantra or Picumata Vol: I, Chapters 1-2, 39-40 & 83, Revelation, Ritual and Material Culture in an Early Śaiva Tantra*, p. 160. Four Devīs: Raktā, Karālī, Caṇḍākṣī, Mahocchuṣmā. Four Dūtis: Karālā, Dantura, Bhīmavaktrā, Mahābalā. Six Yoginis: Kroṣṭukī, Vijayā, Gajakarṇā, Mahāmukhī, Cakravegā, Mahānāsā. Eight Mothers: Maheśvarī, Brāhmī, Vaiṣṇavī, Kaumārī, Vaivasvatī, Indrāṇī, Caṇḍikā, Aghorī.

figure in the daily worship of these temples. That means her ritual system in complete format is either lost or modified later on.

Even if Caṇḍā kāpālīnī takes centre space, all the prominence is given to the worship of Kālasaṅkarṣiṇī. Her prominence is understood from the testimony of manuscripts which describe her inner worship in minute detail³¹. Not only that, the daily ritual has got more elements of Kālasaṅkarṣiṇī than other goddesses. The inner worship of Kālasaṅkarṣiṇī is no more in practice now. We may think that her external worship is exactly the same as the inner worship. But the fact is that external rituals have a totally different texture. It is preferably done on the yantra and a few manuscripts of *Piṭāras* provide the details on this form of worship too.³² But interestingly, what is in practice in the Śākta temples is neither of the two mentioned above. It seems that they have reworked and modified the complete system into a new syncretic format in which some elements of the three goddesses are taken and interwoven together. Even in such instance the prominence is given to the worship of Kālasaṅkarṣiṇī. It is not known clearly yet what led them to realign the complete ritual system into a syncretic format. It is postulated that Tippu's attack on Malabar temples would have led them to modify all the rituals into a miniature form, else, time consuming rituals would have become impractical gradually. The possibility of intervention of the local chieftains in the ritual timings also cannot be ruled out. However, the new ritual system has all the components of worship of Caṇḍā kāpālīnī, Kālasaṅkarṣiṇī and Parā but not in equal measure. It is interesting to note that *Piṭāras* possess manuscripts of complete ritual procedure of goddesses Kālasaṅkarṣiṇī, Parā and Tripurā as independent systems. In short, the ritual procedures of Caṇḍākāpālīnī is incomplete.

Krama tantrism: Lineage, Texts and Philosophy

It would be interesting to inquire into what is Krama tantrism is all about i.e., its historical beginnings, lineage³³, major texts

31 I could find only two manuscripts describing her inner rituals in detail. They are Ms.No-17841 E, Trivandrum Oriental Manuscript Library and a palm leaf manuscript located at Shripuram Digital Archives.

32 This argument is based on the manuscripts found at Shripuram Digital Archives.

33 See Navajivan Rastogi, *Krama Tantrism of Kashmir* and Alexis Sanderson,

and how it might have reached Kerala from Kashmir. The Krama system is believed to be originated from Maṅgalādevī (also known as Virasiṃhasvāminī), the leader of yoginis/pīṭheśvarīs. It is from her the teachings went to Śivānandanātha (first half of the ninth century), also known as Avatāranātha, to whom is believed to have revealed at Uḍḍiyāṇa pīṭha, which is traced to the west-north-west of Kashmir to the north of Peshwar.³⁴ Later, Śivānanda passed on the esoteric teachings to three of his female disciples namely, Keyūravatī, Madanikā and Kalyānikā. From them it went to Govindarāja, Bhānuka and Eraka.

Among the above said yoginis, Keyūravatī enjoys a prominent place within Krama tradition. From her the teachings went to Hrasvanātha / Vāmana who is said to have had five disciples. Chakrabhānu is foremost among them, who initiated Abhinavagupta's teacher Bhūtīrāja.³⁵

South Indian history of Krama tantrism begins with Mahāprakāśānanda³⁶. Generally it is held that Śivānanda (the author of Rjvimarśinī commentary on Nityāśodaśīkārṇava) was the forerunner of South Indian Krama Tantrism. But this supposition is to be reconsidered as there is no evidence for Śivānanda's association with the Krama system. But there are quite number of evidences to prove that he was an adept in different branches of Traipurasaṃpradāya. It is Mahāprakāśānanda who initiated Maheśvarānanda alias Gorakṣa,³⁷

Śaiva Exegesis of Kashmir in order to get a complete picture of Krama.

34 Alexis Sanderson, Śaiva Exegesis of Kashmir, p. 265.

35 See Navajivan Rastogi, Krama Tantrism of Kashmir, pp. 154-56.

36 Maheśvarānanda in his auto commentary on Mahārthamañjarī quotes from several works of his teacher Mahāprakāśānanda. They are Manonuśāsana stotra, Mātaṅgi stotra, Saṃvidstotra and Ānandatāṇḍavavilāsa stotra.

37 namo nikhilamālinyavilāpana paṭīyase/
mahāprakāśapādābjaparāgaparamāṇave// Maṅgalaśloka, 6
atha sā kālayogena śivānandasya dhimataḥ/
śiṣyasyopādīśat devī cidadvaitasya niścayaṃ//
krameṇa tacca nāthānāṃ paripātyā bhuvāḥ sthalaṃ/
divyasiddhamanuṣyaughaprabhāgādavātarat//
avatīrṇāpyasau vidyā mahārthakramagarbhinī/
yogināṃ vadaneṣveva tiṣṭhatyatyantadurlabhā//
atha kālakramavaśāccoladeśāśiromaṇiḥ/
mahāprakāśo nāmāsīd deśiko ḍṛkkriyottaraḥ//
tasya śiṣyobhavat dhīmān gorakṣo nāma vaśyavāk /

the author of the Krama work *Mahārthamañjarī*, into this system. It is through the Maheśvarānanda Krama system that it spreads across South India.³⁸ Even if Maheśvarānanda refers to Māhāprakāśānanda as his teacher, he mentions a Devapāṇin and says that it is whose ritual system of the cycle of worship from sṛṣṭi to bhāsā he had adopted in his text.³⁹ It is to this Devapāṇin, present Krama system of Kerala can be traced. To any available texts of Krama system the unique mantra deities worshipped in Bhāsācakra by *Piṭāras* could not be traced so far except, to a single manuscript (Ms.No-17841 E) located at the oriental manuscript library. In the opening benedictory verses it pays homage to the teachers who fall within the preceptorial lineage beginning with Sathyanātha. Then he is followed by Devapāṇin.⁴⁰ Quite interestingly, the procedures of inner worship and mantra deities described therein exactly matches with that of *Piṭāras*. Therefore it is inferred that it is the system of Devapāṇin whom Maheśvarānanda referred to in his *Mahārthamañjarī*, *Piṭāras* probably have inherited. Nothing is known about Devpāṇin except these references by his name.

The characteristic feature of South Indian Krama tradition is that, unlike that of Kashmir, it is more syncretic in the sense that a group of similar traditions like Trika, Kaula and Tripurā form part of the same lineage. Such an amalgamation of varying cults in a single system can be seen right from Śivānanda himself. Hence, the lineage to which Maheśvarānanda belonged is not Krama alone but was a confluence of several non-dualistic traditions. If we look at the range of works composed by these teachers like Śivānanda, Mahāprakāśānada and Maheśvarānanda, we will see that they were not masters of a single cult alone but of all non-dualistic śākta-śaiva traditions originated in Kashmir. This same conclusion can be reached at with regard to piṭāras

maheśvarānanda iti prāptapūjyāhvayo mahān //

38 Apart from Mahārthamañjarī, Mahārthodaya is the other work attributed to him on Krama system. His other works include: Pādukodaya, Saṃvidullāsa, Parāstotra, Komalavallivilāsa, Mukundakelī, Kuṇḍalābharāṇa and Nakhapratāpa. Navajivan Rastogi, Krama Tantrism of Kashmir, pp. 216-17.

39 tatroddiṣṭabhaṅgyā sṛṣṭyādi bhāsāntaṃ cakraṃ
srīdevapāṇisaṃpradāyānupraviṣṭaiḥ asmābhiranusandhīyate, na
punaretadviparyayeṇa/ Parimala, p. 104.

40 Then he is followed by Ādisiṃha, Śāntinātha, Kerava, Īsanātha, Viśvānanda and Śaktyānanda..

also, as they do inherit non-dualist śākta- śaiva cults of Kashmir. The major difference is that the Tripurā cult among of the *Piṭāras* can be seen gradually waning. But fact is that the manuscripts of Śrīcakrapūja found preserved in some of these households have everything intact. It is lost over the course of time.

Mark S.G Dyczkowski identifies four stages of development of krama soteriology and ritual system. The first stage according to him is characterised by worship of numerous forms of Kālī and Kālasaṅkarṣiṇī is just one of her major forms. Jayadrathayāmala presents this earliest form of worship of Kālī, which even predates the Jñānanetra, foremost teacher of Krama lineage.

The second stage is marked by its association with Kaulism, which has been developed by Matsyendranātha as an independent system. The association with Kaula tradition resulted in the accommodation of Matsyendranātha in the sthīcakra of Krama ritual along with his twelve disciples (rājaputras).

Third phase is represented by the texts like *Devīpañcaśataka* and *Kramasadbhāva*. These texts lay emphasis on the worship of Kālasaṅkarṣiṇī and Śuṣkā.

The fourth stage starts with Jñānanetra, who is known to have authored *Yonigahvara* and *Kālikāstotra*. This phase is characterised by worship of numerous yoginis which reaches its pinnacle by the time of *Mahānayaprakāśa*. These texts refer to the reality as Mahārtha by which the system is known later.⁴¹

Among the four stages observed by Dyczkowski, *Piṭāras* system of worship represents the fourth stage, the mahārtha. What is more interesting is that earlier the Krama school was known as Mahārtha since *Jadarathayāmala* up to *Mahānayaprakāśa*, but in the ritual system of *Piṭāras* the central goddess Kālasaṅkarṣiṇī herself is found designated as Mahārtha.

It is assumed that the Krama system might have reached around 13th to 15th century A.D in Kerala. This assumption is made based on the fact that if we take lower limit as the time of Maheśvarānanda

41 Khacakrapañcakastotra, Hymn to the Five Spheres of Emptiness: Introduction, Edition and Translation, pp. 69-71.

(13th century A.D) and upper limit as that of Cennās Śāṅkaran Nambūtiripadu. No other evidence has come down to us till now to prove its existence even before the 13th century A.D.

Krama philosophy and Ritual

The refinement of discursive thoughts (*vikalpasaṃskāra*) is the central aspect of Krama epistemology.⁴² It postulates that everything be it *saṃvit*, empirical cognition, reflective meditation or cosmic emanation undergo a succession (Krama). Scriptures of this tradition put forward three modes for reaching nirvikalpa state of consciousness. They are *kathana*, *pūjana* and *saṃkramaṇa* respectively. Among these the *kathana* is imparting the traditional secret through oral means. The *pūjana* is worshipping the cycle of consciousness either internally or on an external substratum. The *saṃkramaṇa* is a direct transmission of knowledge from a master to disciple through intense form of descent of grace.⁴³ The *pūjana* is considered to be the lowest of the three modes and which is capable of leading practitioner to the *saṃkramaṇa* gradually.

The piṭhāras possess a unique *pūjanakrama* which however, came to be associated with temples. Though the *pūjana krama* found in the fundamental scriptures like *Jayadrathayāmala*, *Devīdvayardhaśatikā*, *Kramasadbhāva Kālikulakarmārcana* and *Mahārthamañjarī* it slightly differs from each other. Eventually, this ritual system gets consolidated, particularly by the time of *Mahānayaprāśa*.

The cardinal features of Krama worship are: piṭhācakra, pañcavāhakrama, mūrticakra, prakāśacakra, ānandacakra, vṛndacakra, sṛṣṭikrama, sthitikrama, saṃhārakrama, anākhyākrama

42 According to the Krama scriptures the highest reality is the experience of Nirvikalpa state. *asti nānyā gatiṣeṣāṃ viklapagrāsasāhasāt/ I. 32 Mahānayaprakāśa*, TVM. Vikalpas, discursive thoughts are root causes of all worldly suffering and emancipation. Here the mokṣa is considered to be just another mental construction just like suffering. These two mental constructions arise out of the influence of discursive thoughts that give birth to all kinds of duality. (*mithyāvikalpajanitau kila bandhamokṣau / I.3, Mahānayaprakāśa*, TVM.

43 *kathanātmā saṃpradāyo niṣṭhāmatra parāṃ gataḥ/ kathanāt saṃśayacchedaḥ pūjanam paripūrṇatā// VII. 61 saṃkramāt sāmarasyasya parā niṣṭhā pravartate // VII. 62, Mahānayaprakāśa*, TVM.

and bhāsākrama.

Internal ritual (kulaprakriyā) procedures found in the manuscripts of *Piṭāras* follow the above said order precisely. But this as such is not practised by piṭāras today. Instead, some elements of it are accommodated into the daily ritual leaving all other cardinal aspects of the system ritual like mūrticakra, prakāśacakra, ānandacakra, vṛndacakra, sṛṣṭikrama, sthitikrama, saṃhārakrama, anākhyākrama and bhāsākrama. What is more pathetic is that present generation of *Piṭāras* are not even aware of the existence of a full-blown Krama ritual in their possession.

The daily routine of these temple rituals consist of four rituals i.e, *uṣaḥ pūjā*, *etirttu pūjā*, *uccappūjā* and *attāzappūjā*. In the *uṣaḥ pūjā* the goddess Bhadrakālī, the external phase of the temple worship, is worshipped. Among these four rituals *uccappūjā* is the most elaborate one in which Caṇḍā kāpālīnī, Kālasaṅkarṣiṇī, Parā, Bhadrakālī (Rurujit), Mātr̥s, Vaṭukabhairava and all retinues of goddesses are worshipped with alcohol and meat. After the morning rituals, the sword *nāndaka* is taken out of sanctum sanctorum and placed on a seat at *mukhamaṇḍapa* in Kalarivatukkal and Matayikkavu temples. The sword remains there till the afternoon rituals get over. The sword *nāndaka* represents the goddess Bhadrakālī, for she is worshipped on it. The sword is the only ritual substratum taken outside of the temple even for processions during festive season. It also proves the fact that the external phase of the worship of *Piṭāras* revolves around Bhadrakālī, whereas the pantheon of inner worship is kept secret within the sanctum sanctorum. So these temples are venues where inner non-dualistic and outer dualistic ritual realms co-exist and complement each other. The inner realm is more concerned with practitioners' spiritual elevation whereas the outer realm is associated with well-being of the King, kingdom and the public.

Exoteric Dimension

The worship of Bhadrakālī (Rurujit) of these temples can be found adopted from *Mātr̥sadbhāva*, a ritual manual of unknown author. In twenty eight chapters it expounds the rituals of Bhadrakālī from [ācāryavarāṇa up](#) to jīrṇoddhāra.⁴⁴ Quite a number of times it refers to
44 ācāryalakṣaṇādyantu jīrṇoddhārāvasānakam / I. 12 a.

*Brahmayāmala*⁴⁵ as its source text and draws materials heavily from it. Unfortunately, the available copies of *Brahmayāmala* are incomplete and highly corrupted. Its copies, but fragments, are found in Oriental Manuscripts Library, Trivandrum and IFP, Pondicherry.

According to *Brahmayāmala* the goddess is worshipped for the victory of kings in battle or prosperity of the kingdom. It attests that when she is found installed alone in the sanctum sanctorum (*ekaberam*), she stands for the victory of the king and destruction of enemies. When she is with *Saptamātr̥s* (*bahuberam*), the primary concern is the quelling of the dangers and restoration of well-being.⁴⁶ It is to be noted that unlike the interpretation of Āgamic texts, here the terms *ekabera* and *bahubera* have different connotations.⁴⁷ Among the Śākta temples mentioned above, most of them belong to *ekabera* system, only one or two are there that of *bahuvera*. The goddess of *ekabera* is also known as *ekavīri/ekaberī* in *Brahmayāmala* and identified with *Dārukajit*,⁴⁸ one who killed the demon *Dārūka*. Interestingly, it does not mention the other form of the goddess, namely *Rurujit*.

Time and again it emphasizes on the point that those who are born to the lineage of *Pāraśava* / *Pāraśaiva* only are entitled to worship this goddess.⁴⁹ The *Pāraśava-s* are those who are born to a Brahmin father in the woman of a śūdra caste.⁵⁰ He must be well versed in the cult of *ekavīri* in particular and *Mātr̥tantra-s* in general, also should be an adept in Śaiva, *Pāśupata* and *Somasiddhānta*.⁵¹ The sole means of

45 brahmayāmalatantreṣu yathoktaṃ parameṣṭhinā // V. 1.; tasminstu yāmale brahme brahmaproktāḥ kriya daśa // X. 48; etānyatra samuktāni tantresmin brahmayāmaḷe // XII. 39

46 jayārthaṃ śatrunāśārthaṃ ekaberam praśamsitam/
śāntipuṣṭikārthaṃ tu bahuveramudāhṛtam / II., IFP.

47 yatraiva bhadrakālī syādekaberamiti smṛtam //
sā yatra...matṛbhiḥ syād svarūpeṇa pṛthak bhūtā ca smṛtam/
bahuveram tu tannāmnā sthāpanābhedacoditam// II.

48 ekavīriti nāmnāsyād dārukāsuraśāsinī;
dārukasya vadhodbhūtā lalātotsṛṣṭīkīrtitā /
evaṃ vidhipraktavyaṃ ekavīri manoramā// III.

49 pāraśavakule jāto snānam kṛtvā viśeṣataḥ; pūjakastviti vikhyātaṃ samjñā
pāraśavātmanām; parārthamātr̥pūjārthaṃ kuryāt pāraśivānvayaḥ /

50 Śūdrakanyādvijānāntu udbhavo śāstrapāṭhakaḥ /
Sarvatantrasamācāra pāraśaivā prakīrtitāḥ //

51 Brahmacārī grhasthaśca vānaprasthaśca bhikṣukaḥ /
Śaivam pāśupataṃ somaṃ trayasiddhāntameva ca //

livelihood for *Pāraśava* is the worship of *Bhadrakālī*.⁵² And again it is very particular about the caste of the assistants (*mūrtipāḥ*) in ritual that they should also be belonging to the *Pāraśava* community.⁵³ Being this the case, Varrier community of Kerala are referred to as *Pāraśava* in the scriptures but they are not known to be the worshippers of *Bhadrakālī* and do not have any *Bhadrakālī* temple under their possession. So, textual references do not match with facts at least in this case. Moreover, the priests and chief custodians of *Kālī* temples are *Piṭāras* who are Śākta brahmins. Except the matter of caste identity, rest of the details on temple structure and pantheon laid down in *Brahmayāmala* match remarkably well with the Śākta temples of Kerala.

The *Māṭṛsadbhāva* gives detailed account of rituals of *Rurujiṭ*, but does not provide any details of that of *Dārukajit*, except a short description of the fierce battle held between the demon *Dāruka* and the goddess. It does not even differentiate one form from the other i.e., *Rurujiṭ* from *Dārukajit*. But the *Brahmayāmala* clearly demarcates both by giving technical details of either forms.⁵⁴ Nevertheless, *Māṭṛsadbhāva* and *Śeṣasamuccaya* did not carry these technical details forward. Hence, in order to get a complete picture of *Rurujiṭ* worship, one has to read these three texts together.

In all probability, the author of *Māṭṛsadbhāva* might be a Keralite and someone belonged to the *Piṭāra* family. Internal evidence corroborates this assumption. They are:

1. The text bears close affinity with *Prayogamañjarī*,⁵⁵ a Keralite works on temple rituals. It proves his affiliation with Kerala.

2. Reference to *samayavidyā*⁵⁶, *śūlodakavidhi*,⁵⁷ *rudraśakti*,⁵⁸ *pada*,
52 praśastā sarvakāryāṇāṃ māṭṛpūjopajivikāḥ / V. 2; bhadrakālīm samāśritya jīveyuḥ pūjakāḥ sṛtāḥ //

53 mantrajñāiḥ kuśalaiḥ śuddhaiḥ brahmayāmalatatparaiḥ // VII.

pāraśaivakulodbhūtaiḥ māṭṛdikṣāsamanvitaiḥ
54 see Ajithan. P.I, *Rurujiṭ Temples of Kerala : A Religious Site of Co-existence of Krama Tantrism of Kashmir and Māṭṛtantra of Brahmayāmala*, pp. 60-61.

55 see Muralikrishnan M.V, *Critical Edition and Study of Māṭṛsadbhāva*, (unpublished thesis, 2020)

56 navākṣaram tathā sāṅgaṃ vidyāñca samayādikām / XII. 68 a; māṭṛvidyāñca gāyatrīm vidyāñca samayādikām // XXVIII. 32

57 It is the subject matter of the nineteenth chapter. The purifying rituals of śūlodaka are similar to that of viśeṣārghya śodhana of Krama ritual.

58 punaḥ śrīrudraśaktintu smṛtvā sṛṣṭikramaṃ bhajet / XIV. 72 a.

piṇḍa, *rūpa* and *rūpātīta*⁵⁹ etc. shows the author's knowledge of Krama, Trika and Kaula ritualistic traditions. There is no evidence to prove that orthodox Brahmin tantrins of Kerala were aware of Trika and Krama systems.

3. Moreover, the name of the text, *Māṭṛsadbhāva*, itself shows author's preference to link it with the Krama goddess Kālasaṅkarṣiṇī. All these technical details add weightage to the above argument.

Later, what the author of Śeṣasamuccaya did was solely providing a detailed account of worship of Rurujiit as is suitable to the temple ritual cult of Kerala. He, knowingly or unknowingly, got rid of all the elements of Krama, except *samayavidyā*, which he mistook for that of Tripura cult. The fact is that the mantra that he has illustrated as of *samayavidyā* is not found in any of the texts of Tripurā cult.⁶⁰ Secondly, the mantra is closely associated with worship of Tripurasundarī which is not at all fitting to the context of worship of Rurujiit. In addition to it, none of the deities mentioned in the *samayavidyā* has any place in the worship of Rurujiit. So, it can be stated that the author of Śeṣasamuccaya had missed the Krama context of the worship of the Rurujiit completely. What he did was modifying simple ritual procedures laid down in *Māṭṛsadbhāva* into complex format aligning to *Tantrasamuccaya* model of presentation. Hence, in effect, the worship of Rurujiit was decontextualized and made favourable to the tantric ritual model of Kerala brahmins.

Foregoing discussions amply demonstrate the extent complexity involved in the ritual system of *Piṭāras*. They inherit a great tradition in which many undercurrents of Śāktism, developed in North and South India, can be seen interwoven together in perfect harmony. This cult is something very unique and unparalleled. But dearth of sources makes further exploration more challenging. If we could succeed in finding the missing links of this great tradition, it will unravel the mysteries of

59 *ṣoḍaśāntaṃ tato nītvā tadpadārthaṅca bhāvayet /
sthānadhātuyutaṃ bhūyaḥ pade piṇḍaṃ niyojayet //XIV. 70
padaṃ rūpe tathā rūpaṃ rūpātīte tu niṣkale /*

60 I could not trace the *samayavidyā* as is given in the Śeṣasamuccaya to any of the texts of Tripurā cult. Saubhāgyamañjarī, the basic text of tripurā worship of Piṭāras mentions in detail the mantra of *samayavidyā*, but it is no way similar to that of Śeṣasamuccaya.

intellectual and religious exchange held between Kashmir and Kerala.

Conclusion

The primary concern of this paper is to bring to light hitherto unexplored recess of a ritual cult, which has direct links with *Krama* tradition of Kashmir. The *Piṭāras/Mūssads* are hereditary custodians of Śākta temples of Kerala and whose religious practices have two different dimensions. They brought their cultic deities to these temple sites, who are worshipped with soteriological emphasis, as taught in the *Krama* scriptures. On the other exoteric level, they worship Bhadrakālī along with Sapta/Aṣṭamātr̥s for the victory of kings in the battles as well as for the prosperity of regional kingdom. So here the inner world of spiritual seekers and outer world aiming at mundane success meet together in a ritual system of *Piṭāras*. At present, all these temples are venues of conflicts which arose when these ritual spaces were encroached by dominant Brahmins solely with the political motive to extend their dominance to all religious territories. The only way ahead is that the Devaswom board of Kerala has to intervene and take all necessary steps to preserve such a unique system in its purity and provide all moral support to chief custodians of these temples to learn and preserve their system intact.

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KIRANĀVALĪ
Journal of Sanskrit Research Foundation
The New Trivandrum Sanskrit Series Vol. XIV.
Book III-IV
JULY – DECEMBER 2022

ISSN 0975-4067

Printed and published by: Dr.C.S.Sasikumar, Secretary, Sanskrit Research Foundation, Thiruvananthapuram, for Sanskrit Research Foundation, Thiruvananthapuram-36
Sanskritresearchfoundation@gmail.com